

8 Abstract

9 The deposition of carbonate rocks is closely tied to Earth’s climate and ocean chemistry.
 10 Healthy carbonate platforms produce sediment at a rate that usually keeps up with ac-
 11 commodation changes due to tectonic subsidence and sea level rise. In contrast, plat-
 12 form ‘drowning’ during Ocean Anoxic Events (OAEs) has long been considered a phys-
 13 ical expression of biogeochemical changes that reduce shallow-water sedimentation rates.
 14 Identifying the exact mechanism(s) that contribute to platform drowning are critical for
 15 understanding the nature and duration of environmental disruptions during these events.

16 Here we present a new model for long-term platform drowning based on changing
 17 oceanic gradients in alkalinity and carbonate saturation states. Well-oxygenated oceans
 18 are characterized by steep gradients in saturation state with high rates of carbonate ‘over-
 19 production’ in the surface ocean and dissolution in the deep ocean. Under reducing con-
 20 ditions, anaerobic microbial metabolisms act to reduce these gradients so that there is
 21 less overproduction in the surface ocean which may manifest locally as slower accumu-
 22 lation rates in tropical shallow-water settings. Simple box models show that this is a quasi-
 23 steady state process that lasts as long for as long an anoxic condition persist, effectively
 24 coupling the timescales of carbonate sedimentation and redox changes. We posit that
 25 redox-based changes in ocean gradients act alongside other kill mechanisms to produce
 26 the diversity of platform drowning patterns observed in the rock record both in Meseo-
 27 zoic OAEs and for older hyperthermal events.

28 1 Introduction

29 Carbonate sediments are physical products of Earth’s biogeochemical cycles. Con-
 30 sequently, major shifts in carbonate sediments often accompany intense biogeochemical
 31 changes, providing clues as to their nature (e.g., Hoffman et al., 1998). Several well-known
 32 examples occur in strata spanning Ocean Anoxic Events (OAEs), a series of carbon cy-
 33 cle changes that perturbed Mesozoic climate and ocean redox (Arthur et al., 1987; Jenkyns,
 34 2010; Schlanger & Jenkyns, 1976; Scholle & Arthur, 1980). In shallow-water carbonates,
 35 OAEs are marked by carbonate platform ‘drowning’ in which deeper, organic-rich de-
 36 posits displaced shallow-water facies (Arthur & Schlanger, 1979; Schlager, 1981; Phelps
 37 et al., 2015)(Fig. 1a). Schlager (1981) christened this the ‘paradox of drowned platforms’
 38 because growth rates in modern carbonates exceed all but the fastest rates of sea level
 39 rise. Hallock and Schlager (1986) provided an initial solution that invoked reduced sed-
 40 imentation rates, and subsequent research has focused on chemical and biological mech-
 41 anisms that hinder carbonate growth. Such mechanisms are critical for understanding
 42 the nature of environmental changes at OAEs because they provide a common factor link-
 43 ing geochemical records, platform drowning, and biotic turnover among calcifying organ-
 44 isms (Föllmi et al., 1994; Kiessling & Simpson, 2011; Krencker et al., 2020; Phelps et al.,
 45 2015; Trecalli et al., 2012).

46 OAEs are complex events in which a single cause—usually an injection of volcanic
 47 CO₂—triggers a cascade of related events that could cause platform drowning (Jenkyns,
 48 2010). Early work by Hallock and Schlager (1986) pointed to dissolved nutrients as likely
 49 drowning agents because many photosymbiotic reef-builders are well-adapted to low nu-
 50 trient conditions. Under this hypothesis, elevated nutrient fluxes drown platforms by stim-
 51 ulating primary production, decreasing light penetration and allowing fleshy non-calcifiers
 52 to out-compete carbonate producers. This drowning mechanism is attractive because in-
 53 creased nutrients and primary productivity are also used to explain geochemical prox-
 54 ies for redox and weathering (Blättler et al., 2011; Jenkyns, 2010; Lechler et al., 2015).
 55 However, excess nutrients may simply shift carbonate sedimentation towards non-skeletal
 56 components (e.g., ooids and microbialites) which can comprise a significant portion of
 57 platform sediments near OAEs (Ettinger et al., 2020; Huck et al., 2010; Krencker et al.,
 58 2020). Nutrient-related drowning implies that non-skeletal carbonates accumulate more

59 slowly than the facies they replace, which may not be universally true given high rates
60 of microbial reef production elsewhere in the Phanerozoic (e.g., Franceschi et al., 2016).

61 Another plausible mechanism for reduced carbonate production near OAEs is ocean
62 acidification (Kiessling & Simpson, 2011) (Fig.1b). By analogy to anthropogenic climate
63 change, volcanic CO₂ invades the surface ocean over short timescales, causing a drop in
64 pH and the saturation states of calcite and aragonite (Zeebe & Wolf-Gladrow, 2001). While
65 acidification has been invoked for many carbon cycle perturbations, there are several is-
66 sues with implicating it as the sole driver of platform drowning. First, Earth’s climate
67 system has a negative feedback which negates ocean acidification over timescales longer
68 than 10 ky (Hönisch et al., 2012; Knoll et al., 2011). In contrast, many platform drown-
69 ing events and intervals of biotic turnover occur over intervals exceeding 100 ky. Second,
70 carbon is well-mixed on millennial timescales such that the onset of ocean acidification
71 should be synchronous, yet stratigraphic records for OAEs vary through both time and
72 space (Heldt et al., 2010)(Fig. 1). Together these factors suggest the role of additional
73 processes in platform drowning.

74 A third mechanism for platform drowning can be inferred from microbial metabolisms,
75 which link Earth’s large-scale redox and acid-base cycles. In general, anaerobic respira-
76 tion pathways produce alkalinity which locally increases the carbonate saturation state.
77 As such, many studies focus on anoxia as a possible driver of enhanced carbonate pre-
78 cipitation (Grotzinger & Knoll, 1995). However, a small subset of studies has instead con-
79 sidered the role of anaerobic metabolisms in setting alkalinity gradients in the ocean. In
80 this framework, anaerobic metabolisms buffer the deep ocean against dissolution at the
81 expense of oversaturation in surface waters (Higgins et al., 2009; Knoll et al., 2011) (Fig.
82 1c). Although these studies mostly dealt with the long-term evolution of ocean redox,
83 Higgins et al. (2009) suggested that similar concepts could be used to interpret patterns
84 in carbonate sedimentation during Phanerozoic carbon cycle perturbations such as OAEs.
85 Here we present a simple box model for platform drowning that links platform drown-
86 ing to ocean anoxia by way of changing alkalinity gradients. We simulate the onset and
87 dissipation of ocean anoxia by varying the ratio of alkalinity to dissolved inorganic car-
88 bon (DIC) produced during respiration. Our results suggest that widespread sulfate re-
89 duction would shift the locus of carbonate away from the surface ocean, resulting in slower
90 overall sedimentation rates in shallow-water settings.

91 2 Background

92 2.1 Carbonate production and dissolution in the Earth surface environ- 93 ments

94 The formation of carbonate rocks is the primary sink by which the products of weath-
95 ering, especially alkalinity, are removed from natural waters and seawater. Over geologic
96 timescales, seawater achieves a sort of quasi-steady state in which the outgassing and
97 weathering fluxes of inorganic carbon and alkalinity is balanced by the formation of car-
98 bonate rocks in net (Walker et al., 1981; D. Archer et al., 1997):

$$F_{weathering} = F_{burial} \quad (1)$$

99 A naive interpretation of Eqn. 1 is that the surface ocean produces exactly as much car-
100 bonate as it needs to balance the alkalinity budget imposed by weathering . In fact, mod-
101 ern oceans produce carbonate minerals at a rate that is four times higher than weath-
102 ering input (Broecker et al., 1982; Sarmiento & Gruber, 2006; Sigman & Boyle, 2000).
103 The ‘overproduction’ of carbonate is compensated by carbonate dissolution within deep
104 ocean basins and in shallow oxic porewaters more broadly (Walter & Burton, 1990; Broecker,
105 1998):

$$F_{weathering} = F_{prod} - F_{diss} = F_{burial} \quad (2)$$

106 While Eqns. 1 and 2 are equivalent, the latter hints that there may be multiple com-
 107 binations of precipitation/dissolution which satisfy the geological steady state condition.
 108 While many studies (e.g., Zeebe & Westbroek, 2003) have investigated how carbonate
 109 chemistry and production responds to changes in weathering fluxes, Higgins et al. (2009)
 110 considered the special case of a fixed weathering flux ($F_{weathering}$). Under this scenario,
 111 a steady state characterized by reduced rates of carbonate dissolution would be balanced
 112 by reduced carbonate (over)production in the surface ocean, with a potential corollary
 113 of lower surface ocean saturation states.

114 A reasonable question, then, is what factors drove patterns of precipitation and dis-
 115 solution in the past. Carbonate dissolution in the modern ocean is governed by both abi-
 116 otic and biological factors. Some carbonate dissolves at depth because carbonate min-
 117 erals are more soluble at low temperatures and high pressures (Zeebe & Wolf-Gladrow,
 118 2001), but a substantial amount of dissolution is driven by aerobic respiration of organic
 119 matter, both in the water column and within sedimentary pore fluids (D. E. Archer, 1996;
 120 Dunne et al., 2012; Hales, 2003). Biologically-driven dissolution is widespread in the mod-
 121 ern oceans because oxygenated bottom waters overlie >95% of the seafloor (Helly & Levin,
 122 2004). However, oxygen was not as ubiquitous in the past, and oceans characterized by
 123 high rates of anaerobic respiration experienced less dissolution—or even net precipita-
 124 tion—in porewaters and parts of the deep ocean (Bergmann et al., 2013; Higgins et al.,
 125 2009; Knoll et al., 2016). By Eqn. 2, a switch to more anaerobic conditions (less disso-
 126 lution) during OAEs could reduce production in the surface ocean if 1) the weathering
 127 input to the surface ocean is relatively constant and 2) the ocean-atmosphere system has
 128 negative feedbacks that push the system from one steady state to another. If the shallow-
 129 water sedimentation rate tracks local surface chemistry, rather than the global burial rate,
 130 then re-organizing patterns of precipitation and dissolution in the ocean may lead to slower
 131 local accumulation rates in platforms.

132 2.2 OAEs and the extent of ocean anoxia

133 Testing the redox-drowning hypothesis for OAEs requires quantitative data on the
 134 extent of ocean anoxia. Mass-balance studies of redox-sensitive elements can, in prin-
 135 ciple, provide such constraints, typically rendered as a percentage of the seafloor over-
 136 lain by anoxic conditions. Such estimates vary substantially by proxy and material dur-
 137 ing the same event. For example, the maximum extent of seafloor anoxia during OAE
 138 2 was calculated as 1-2% from $\delta^{238}\text{U}$ in shales (Montoya-Pino et al., 2010), 8-15% from
 139 $\delta^{238}\text{U}$ in carbonates (Clarkson et al., 2018), and 40% from $\epsilon^{205}\text{Tl}$ in shales (Ostrander
 140 et al., 2017). However, trace element proxies have different oxygen thresholds for draw-
 141 down and enrichment, so percentages calculated by through different proxies may not
 142 be interchangeable (Clarkson et al., 2018).

143 Another estimate for the extent of anoxia can be derived from biomarkers derived
 144 from specific groups of sulfur-oxidizing phototrophs (*Chlorobiaceae*) (Forster et al., 2008;
 145 Kuypers et al., 2002; Pancost et al., 2004). These biomarkers track water-column eux-
 146 inia as they strongly suggest that free H_2S was both present and sufficiently abundant
 147 within the photic zone (Damsté & Köster, 1998). For OAE 2, biogeochemical paleoceanog-
 148 raphic models calibrated to biomarkers suggest at least 50% of the seafloor was anoxic
 149 during peak OAE conditions (Monteiro et al., 2012). Biomarker data are particularly
 150 important as they provide direct evidence that the $\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{SO}_4$ redox pair played an ex-
 151 panded role in photosynthesis and respiration at the expense of $\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Together, the
 152 percentages calculated from trace elements and biomarkers provide a range of conditions
 153 with which to calibrate the platform drowning model.

3 Model setup

We treated carbonate production and dissolution in marine basins with a simple two-box scheme that tracks fluxes of alkalinity (A) and dissolved inorganic carbon (C) following the scheme of Bergmann et al. (2013) and Higgins et al. (2009). In this idealized calculation, the equations for alkalinity balance (A) in the surface (A_1) and deep (A_2) ocean are:

$$\frac{dA_1}{dt} = \frac{1}{V_1}[A_i - 2F_{prod} - F_o\Delta_{alk} + J\nabla A] \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dA_2}{dt} = \frac{1}{V_2}[2F_{diss} + F_o\Delta_{alk} - J\nabla A] \quad (4)$$

The coupled carbon equations are:

$$\frac{dC_1}{dt} = \frac{1}{V_1}[C_i - F_{prod} - F_o\Delta_{alk} + J\nabla C] \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dC_2}{dt} = \frac{1}{V_2}[F_{diss} + F_o\Delta_{alk} - J\nabla C] \quad (6)$$

Alkalinity is supplied to the surface ocean by weathering (A_i) and removed by carbonate precipitation (F_{prod}). Some carbonate is dissolved in the deep ocean and porewaters, returning alkalinity to the system (F_{diss}). Carbonate production and dissolution within each box was described by a rate law of saturation state, Ω :

$$F_{prod} \propto (\Omega_{surface} - 1)^2 \quad (7)$$

$$F_{prod} \propto (1 - \Omega_{deep})^2 \quad (8)$$

In turn, the average saturation states in each reservoir were taken as a function of alkalinity and dissolved inorganic carbon, which were solved at each step using the solver implemented in CO2sys (Lewis & Wallace, 1998). By charge and/or mass conservation, any process that changes the concentrations of alkalinity and dissolved inorganic carbon in either box will also affect the carbonate precipitation and dissolution fluxes by way of Ω .

Beyond carbonate precipitation and dissolution, we considered two additional processes that transfer alkalinity and carbon between the surface and deep ocean boxes. Physical exchange by advection and/or diffusion (J) transfers alkalinity and DIC according to the gradient, ∇A , between the two boxes. The second transfer mechanism is associated with an advective organic matter flux, F_o (i.e. the sedimentation of biological particles associated with the biological pump as well as omnipresent co-deposition of organic matter associated with fine sediment). Inorganic carbon is consumed in surface waters by photosynthesis and returned at depth through respiration/remineralization. This process also re-distributes alkalinity because metabolic processes either generate or consume alkalinity to a degree based on the identity of the participating redox pair. Rather than track individual redox species, we use the net ratios of DIC:alkalinity change, Δ_{alk} . Relevant Δ_{alk} ratios balanced for typical marine organic matter by Bergmann et al. (2013) are shown in Figure 2.

4 Results

Using the modern ocean basins as a starting point, the model was used to investigate the effects of changing Δ_{alk} on carbonate precipitation and dissolution. The default steady state was benchmarked to approximate the modern ocean by setting $\Delta_{alk} = 0$ and by setting the carbonate flux out of the surface ocean, F_c , to four times the weathering flux, A_i . Based on geological and geochemical constraints on the timing and severity of anoxia associated with OAEs, we considered an OAE as a 200ky period of reduced oxygen availability ($\Delta_{alk} = 0.6$) with 50 ky onset and recovery periods (Fig. 3a). Dimensionalizing the model in this way, the point is not to simulate the complexity of OAE events, but to assess the potential impact of coupling of the carbonate system to known redox changes that empirical observations from the sedimentary record evolve over timescales from 10-100 ky. After the 50 ky transition interval, the carbonate system settled into a new steady state that persisted until Δ_{alk} changes again. As expected, the new steady state was characterized by lower Ω and lower rates of carbonate production in the surface ocean (Fig. 3b,c).

Importantly, the time-dependant changes in carbonate precipitation in Fig. 3a-c appeared to reach quasi-steady state over timescales of >10 ky. When the steady state solutions were treated as functions of Δ_{alk} , the resulting plots related the magnitude of potential platform drowning to the extent of anoxia with reasonable simplifying assumptions. First, we considered a simplified case of two redox pairs— O_2/H_2O and H_2S/SO_4^- —so that the horizontal axis represents a weighted mixture between the two Δ_{alk} vectors. If the percentage of aerobic respiration replaced by sulfate reduction is roughly analogous to the percentage of the seafloor covered by anoxic bottom waters, then the maximum Δ_{alk} value can be estimated from studies of redox-sensitive elements and biomarkers (Section 2.2). Second, we assumed that the sedimentation rate for shallow-water platforms closely follows the overproduction of the surface ocean rather than the global average, (F_{prod}), which is the same among all valid steady state solutions. Under these assumptions, carbonate accumulation decreases with the spread of ocean anoxia, presenting a plausible mechanism for platform drowning.

5 Discussion

The simple model presented above highlights the most salient features of the coupled carbonate chemistry redox model in comparison with other drowning mechanisms for OAEs. When Δ_{alk} is perturbed, negative feedbacks in the cycle push the systems towards a new steady state, allowing lower sedimentation rates to be sustained over arbitrarily long timescales (Fig. 3 a-c). In contrast, modeling studies of acidification-overshoot scenarios showed a transient response that decays in <100 ky because weathering feedbacks and carbonate compensation operate over relatively short timescales (D. Archer et al., 1997; Hönisch et al., 2012; Knoll et al., 2011; Payne & Kump, 2007). The redox-drowning model effectively couples carbonate sedimentation to empirical observations of diminished seawater oxygen concentrations and elevated modes of anaerobic respiration and/or nutrient cycles which better match the 250-700 kyr timescale for OAE2 (Kolnick 2005, Sageman et al., 2006, Kuroda et al., 2007) and require only moderate increases in pCO_2 (Clarkson et al., 2018). The redox-drowning model is most similar to the nutrient-drowning hypothesis since many interpretations of OAEs favor increased nutrients and primary productivity as the driver of anoxia. Note that the rate laws used in the model (Eqns. 7-8) are not specific to a particular carbonate factory—and while there may be real differences related to biological turnover and changes in the abundance and ecology of marine calcifiers during these events, that the dynamics can be generalized within a common rate law suggests that the results hold for a variety of skeletal and non-skeletal facies. This generality complements the nutrient-drowning hypothesis, which was calibrated to modern calcifying taxa but does not account for microbial and/or oolitic facies (Ettinger et al., 2020; Huck et al., 2010; Krencker et al., 2020). We note that the redox-drowning

236 model does not exclude other drowning mechanisms, and it likely acts in conjunction with
 237 or as a corollary of other factors. If both mechanisms occurred in an event, then the re-
 238 lative strength of each could combine to create different patterns of platform architec-
 239 ture surrounding OAEs (Fig. 4).

240 Another important aspect of the model results is that the response of carbonate
 241 production is a non-linear function of redox changes-the shape of this function indicated
 242 that significant decreases in carbonate sedimentation can occur during modest expansion
 243 of anoxia. For OAE 2, the concave-up response is important because estimates of
 244 peak anoxic conditions vary widely among proxies. While the lowest estimates of seafloor
 245 anoxia during this interval (1-2, % Montoya-Pino et al., 2010) would produce a negligi-
 246 ble response, a maximum extent of only 15% (Clarkson et al., 2018) would reduce car-
 247 bonate sedimentation to 82% of its initial value. For proxy records that suggest 40-50%
 248 seafloor anoxia during OAE 2 (Monteiro et al., 2012; Ostrander et al., 2017), carbonate
 249 sedimentation rates would fall to approximately half of their original values. While the
 250 model is compatible across a range of proxy records, stratigraphic evidence for especially
 251 widespread or severe drowning events such as OAE2 might favor those higher estimates
 252 of peak seafloor anoxia.

253 We note that the model is purposefully simplified and some caution is required when
 254 upscaling it to the complexity of OAEs in the stratigraphic record. The model isolates
 255 the effects of redox-driven changes in sedimentation by holding weathering and organic
 256 fluxes constant. In reality, increased $p\text{CO}_2$ outgassing will drive a weathering response
 257 that could introduces competing effects into the model. Increased silicate weathering (Blättler
 258 et al., 2011) will increase the alkalinity flux A_i , into the surface ocean and will partially
 259 offset lowered rates of overproduction, at least transiently. However, increased weath-
 260 ering may also increase nutrient budgets and drive increased primary productivity (Monteiro
 261 et al., 2012), and the resulting higher fluxes of organic matter would increase gradients
 262 in DIC and could further impact the distribution of the alkalinity gradient depending
 263 on the nature of organic remineralization and respiration pathways used. Addressing the
 264 relative magnitude and timing of such responses is beyond the scope of this work, although
 265 our model highlights the most basic components at play in a redox-based drowning scen-
 266 ario: carbonate production and dissolution governed by Ω in each cell, reflecting pri-
 267 mary production and advection/sedimentation of organic matter and biogeochemical red-
 268 ox reactions that track changes in alkalinity or proton equivalents. These features could
 269 conceivably be handled by intermediate complexity models such as GENIE (Monteiro
 270 et al., 2012; Ridgwell et al., 2007) and indeed may already be present. These models could
 271 be used to investigate whether redox-based drowning correctly reproduces regional dif-
 272 ferences in platform drowning (Heldt et al., 2010; Phelps et al., 2015; Huck et al., 2010)

273 One key assumption of our model is that, like today, the Cretaceous ocean was char-
 274 acterized by a fourfold overproduction of carbonate in the surface ocean. This raises the
 275 question as to why this overproduction exists and how far back in time it extends. Pre-
 276 vious models (e.g., Zeebe & Westbroek, 2003) have ascribed overproduction to pelagic
 277 forams that can efficiently calcify under very low saturation states. This view empha-
 278 sized the role of biocalifiers and suggests that different controls may have operated prior
 279 to the mid-Mesozoic (Ridgwell, 2005). In contrast, models that emphasize the role of res-
 280 piration on precipitation-dissolution dynamics provide concepts that are useful over much
 281 larger swaths of Earth history (Higgins et al., 2009; Knoll et al., 2016). If carbonate over-
 282 production is largely independent of changes in biocalcification, then redox-based plat-
 283 form drowning could be applied to episodes of platform drowning and recovery associ-
 284 ated with Paleozoic-early Mesozoic anoxic events.

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Figure 1. a. Stratigraphic patterns of Cretaceous platform drowning as summarized by Phelps et al. (2014). b. Ocean acidification by invasion of atmospheric CO_2 . Under this scenario, CO_2 sourced from volcanoes or methane hydrate dissociation make their way into the ocean, reducing the saturation state and causing the CCD to shallow. c. Shifting gradients in saturation states. Depth-dependant Ω gradients are highly dependant on the biological pump and the availability of various electron donor/acceptor pairs (Higgins et al., 2009; Knoll et al., 2011)

Figure 2. Key reactions and their effect on the carbonate system after Bergmann et al. (2013). Δ_{alk} gives the change in alkalinity per mole inorganic carbon produced or consumed during reactions.

Figure 3. Figure 2: Model response to changes in Δ_{alk} . a. Modeling an OAE as a shift in Δ_{alk} away from aerobic respiration ($\Delta_{alk} = 0$) and towards sulfate reduction ($\Delta_{alk} = 1.2$). The maximum shift, $\Delta_{alk} = 0.6$, is equivalent to 50% of aerobic respiration being replaced by sulfate reduction. b. Changes in Ω caused by changes in Δ_{alk} . As Δ_{alk} increases, deep ocean and porewater Ω is buffered against dissolution at the expense of surface ocean Ω . c. Changes in carbonate fluxes associates with changes in Δ_{alk} . Fluxes are normalized to the alkalinity flux into the ocean, A_i , which is assumed to be constant. The surface ocean curve represents the degree of carbonate overproduction needed to balance out dissolution. As Δ_{alk} approaches increases, the degree of overproduction decreases, which can be interpreted as lower sedimentation rates in shallow water settings. Note that the lowered surface fluxes are a new steady state for the system which persists until Δ_{alk} changes again. References for 1c are 1) Montoya-Pino et al. (2010), 2) Clarkson et al. (2018), 3) Ostrander et al. (2017), and 4) Monteiro et al. (2012).

Figure 4. Comparisons between acidification-overshoot and redox-drowning models. The acidification-overshoot model operates over shorter (10-100 ky) timescales. In contrast, the redox-drowning model produces quasi-steady state changes that persist over arbitrarily long timescales. These mechanisms, along with nutrient-driven drowning, are not mutually exclusive; spatial variability and differences in drowning across separate events may be caused by variations in the relative strength of each driver.